

Phylogenomics of Agaricaceae s. l. dedicated to Podaxaceae, *Macropsalliota* and the Asian *Verrucospora*

Kun L. Yang (mugoture@gmail.com; College of Forestry and Landscape Architecture, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

Jia Y. Lin (mycofloscula@gmail.com; College of Plant Protection, South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou 510642, Guangdong, China)

Citation Yang, K.L. & Lin, J.Y. 2025. Phylogenomics of Agaricaceae s. l. dedicated to Podaxaceae, *Macropsalliota* and the Asian *Verrucospora*. *Research sheet of Turemugo Lab (poster)* 4 (10): 102–105.

Copyright © 2025 The author(s). *Research sheet of Turemugo Lab* is a blog series regarding studies of mushroomology running voluntarily (currently it does not have an ISSN!). These contents are distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

Friendly Reminder These contents may become outdated following future academic progress. Please keep an eye on the latest researches.

Text

In previous work on *Hymenagaricus* and *Xanthagaricus*, we noted an unusual clustering of *Podaxa* and *Macrolepiota*, which appeared somewhat discordant with other traditional Agaricaceae taxa (Yang *et al.* 2024a). It was intriguing to later observe a consistent pattern reported in Schultz *et al.* (2024). Consequently, in another work regarding *Leucocoprinus* s. l. plus *Lepiota* and its allies (Yang *et al.* 2024b), we had intended to resurrect Podaxaceae to accommodate *Podaxa* and *Macrolepiota*, distinguishing them from the more narrowly defined Agaricaceae. However, due to insufficient signal from the four DNA loci, it appeared infeasible at that time to resolve this split. This prompted our decision to attempt constructing a genome-scale phylogeny of Agaricaceae s. l. (although more accurately, Lycoperdaceae s. l.).

Interestingly, the numerous collections of *Macropsalliota tropica* from the Pearl River Delta region (Yang & Lin 2025) later became the primary impetus for advancing this dream. Although we considered *Macropsalliota* distinctive in both morphology and sequence patterns, it usually received low support in the four-locus phylogenetic framework, with *M. tropica* representing the most peculiar lineage—and the one lacking complete four-locus data (Yang *et al.* 2024b). After hastily assembling a series of Agaricaceae s. l. collections mostly from our HTBM herbarium and some from the collaborative HKAS herbarium, with the kind assistance of Dr. Zhu L. Yang and other colleagues, we conducted a series of next-generation sequencing. This enabled us to construct the following interesting phylogenomic tree (Figure 1) using 121 orthologous protein sequences by coalescent algorithm with ASTRAL-IV (Zhang *et al.* 2025). As expected, it resolved Podaxaceae represented by *Macrolepiota*, as distinct from Agaricaceae s. str, and several important *Macropsalliota* spp. in a good generic clade.

To further elucidate the phylogenomic position of *Verrucospora*, we also included a collection morphologically identified as *V. verrucispora*, collected in Thailand by Drs. R.

Coalescent tree by 121 orthologous protein sequences

Battarreaceae, Coprinaceae & Mycenastraceae not sampled

Outgroup not shown here

Agaricaceae

Lycoperdaceae

Podaxaceae

Verrucosporaceae
(= Lepiotaceae)

Tulostomataceae
Phelloriniaceae

▲ **Figure 1.** Phylogeny of Agaricaceae s. l. (*Battarreaceae*, *Coprinaceae* & *Mycenastraceae* not sampled) constructed with 121 orthologous protein sequences by coalescent algorithm.

Sanmee and Zhu L. Yang. The results (Figure 1) indicated that it formed a long branch but remained nested within *Lepiota* s. l. Notably, Sarawi *et al.* (2025) published a gorgeous work on the systematics of *Lepiota* s. l. Incorporating their relevant sequences into our four-locus matrix of Agaricaceae s. l., we found that *Lepiotella* ("*Chamaemyces*") and *Verrucospora* were still required to form a monophyletic *Lepiota*. Their placements did not favor dividing the remaining *Lepiota* species into clearly delimited genera, as *Lepiotella* was deeply embedded within sect. *Cristatae*, and *Verrucospora* was insetted

on the backbone of sect. *Stenosporae* (data not shown here). Unless these issues can be resolved by incorporating more molecular loci, reverting *V. verrucispora* to its basionym, *Lepiota verrucispora*, appears justified.

The previously well-known family name Lepiotaceae had been never validly published for a long time, resulting in the unfortunate replacement by Verrucosporaceae, proposed more than a century later. We had overlooked the latter, and inadvertently published a valid and legitimate, yet superfluous name Lepiotaceae (Yang *et al.* 2024b). Recently we surveyed early literature in an attempt to identify any earlier legitimate proposal of Lepiotaceae but found none. However, note that a critical premise still underlying all the above discussion is that the type material of *Lepiota verrucispora*, described from Africa, must be confamilial with the Asian materials now studied. The current assignment of Asian materials to this species is based solely on morphological similarity, without sequenced materials from Africa available for comparison, and thus the assignment remains uncertain. A SEM photo of basidiospores from the Asian collection sequenced for phylogenomics is supplied (Figure 2).

The release of relevant genomic data, along with detailed considerations of incomplete lineage sorting, hybridization and related issues, will be addressed in later publications.

▲ **Figure 2.** Scanning electron microscopic photos by Kun L. Yang of the basidiospores from an Asian collection of *Lepiota verrucispora* (\equiv *Verrucospora verrucispora*) made in Thailand by Drs. R. Sanmee and Zhu L. Yang sequenced for phylogenomic studies shown in Figure 1.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Zhu L. Yang, Hua Qu, Zhi-Jia Gu, R. Sanmee, Jun-Xian He, Zhen-Chao Liu, Xin-Tong Gao, J. Y. Tang and Xin-Sheng Qin for their assistance in this study!

References

- Sarawi, S., Piepenbring, M. & Reschke, K. 2025. Phylogenetic and taxonomic re-assessment of the genera *Echinoderma* and *Lepiota*. *Fungal Systematics and Evolution* 15: 235–263.
- Schultz, T.R., Sosa-Calvo, J., Kveskin, M.P., Lloyd, M.W., Dentinger, B., Kooij, P.W., Vellinga, E.C., Rehner, S.A., Rodrigues, A., Montoya, Q.V., Fernández-Marín, H., Ješovnik, A., Niskanen, T., Liimatainen, K., Leal-Dutra, C.A., Solomon, S.E., Gerardo, N.M., Currie, C.R., Bacci, M., Jr, Vasconcelos, H.L., Rabeling, C., Faircloth, B.C. & Doyle, V.P. 2024. The coevolution of fungus-ant agriculture. *Science* 386 (6717): 105–110.
- Yang, K.L. & Lin, J.Y. 2025. *Macropsalliota tropica* is found in China. *Research sheet of Turemugo Lab (poster)* 4 (8): 94–97.
- Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M., Liu, Z.-C., Hosen, M.I. & Yang, Z.L. 2024a. *Heinemannomyces*, *Hymenagaricus* and *Xanthagaricus* revisited (Basidiomycota, Agaricaceae). *Phytotaxa* 659 (2): 112–164.
- Yang, K.L., Lin, J.Y., Li, G.-M., Li, T.H. & Yang, Z.L. 2024b. Rediscovering *Leucoagaricus sinicus*, with the recognition of *Leucoagaricus* and *Leucocoprinus* as separate genera, and two new genera in Agaricaceae (Basidiomycota). *Phytotaxa* 676 (3): 199–255.
- Zhang, C., Nielsen, R. & Mirarab, S. 2025. ASTER: A package for large-scale phylogenomic reconstructions. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 42 (8): msaf172.